

ISOLATION OF ANTI-ANAEMIC FACTOR PRESENT IN RAW LIVER.

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That raw liver contains a principle potent against pernicious anaemia had been recognised long ago. That this principle is essentially organic in nature, is rendered very probable by the work of Dakin, Karrer and others (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, **77**, 325; 1930, **88**, 428; 1935, **109**, 498; 1928, **77**, 331; 1931, **92**, 117; *Am. J. Physiol.*, 1929, **90**, 316; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1938, **21**, 314; 1937, **20**, 622.) The problem of isolation of the active principle was taken up in 1936 in the Biochemical Laboratory of the King's College, London, and has been continued in the University College of Science, Calcutta. It has now been possible to isolate a purely organic substance which has been proved by clinical tests, to possess powerful reticulocytic activity. It is free from all traces of metals and has been proved to be not an amino-acid. It does not give "Pauly reaction", nor does it respond to the "Ninhydrin test." It is not a polypeptide. The substance contains sulphur and nitrogen and forms a picrate, m.p. 235°. (C, 38.34; H, 2.89; N, 19.38 per cent).

The material was further fractionated by liberating it from the picrate at different pH values in the acid range. The compound isolated at pH 0.5 is highly active and forms a picrate in yellow cubes, m.p. 245°. (Found: N, 20.7 per cent).

The depicrated material is a colourless body, precipitable by phosphotungstic acid and gives pyrrole reaction. By clinical test it has been found to be potent against anaemia either when injected or administered orally. A detailed account of the results will be soon published.

Sulphur forms a part of the constitution of the active material since it gives a crystalline compound with mercuric chloride.

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